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Research and Innovation action (RIA)*

WIMBY

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CMS	Content management system
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
IT	Information Technology
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package
KIP	Key Impact Pathways
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SQL	Structured query language
SEO	Search engine optimisation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Dissemination constitutes one of the core activities of the WIMBY project. To maximise the uptake of information generated by the project different stakeholder groups are identified and communication is tailored to fit each particular stakeholder in terms of channels, content and style.

This document presents the Communication and Dissemination Plan developed to promote the project, raise the awareness on the research topic and increase the visibility of its outcomes. The document illustrates the dissemination goals, the overall dissemination approach and identifies the dissemination actions planned for the project duration; it is designed to be a practical framework for day-to-day communication activities and it will be updated in accordance with the evolution of the project.

The document is organised into 6 sections. Section 1 is an introduction of the project and illustrates the high-level goals of the project and the main action lines. Section 2 is dedicated to the role of communication and dissemination in the WIMBY project and the description of the overall communication and dissemination strategy. Section 3 presents the products and actions, divided into promotional materials, products, online and in person communication activities and all dissemination activities more focused on promoting project results. Section 4 presents how the project intends to monitor and measure the success of the communication and dissemination activities and keep track of their impact. In Section 5 a preliminary editorial plan is presented. Section 6 illustrates the monitoring and evaluation system designed for WIMBY with the goal to keep track of project achievements contributing towards the Key Impact Pathways.

1. PROJECT OVERVIEW

The WIMBY project aims to increase social acceptance of wind power as a renewable energy source by addressing challenges and factors that impede its deployment, such as restrictive regulations and negative public perception. The project uses cutting-edge models to assess the impacts, conflicts, and potentials of wind power development, develops guidelines to increase public engagement and translates the results into practical information for stakeholders.

The WIMBY project adopts a citizen science approach to disseminate its models, data, and results through open-access repositories and social media interaction. The project uses a Web-GIS interactive forum to enhance the content and usability of the information, and involves feedback from various stakeholders.

The focus is on improving wind energy potential assessments by combining techno-economic models with assessments of environmental, security, and health impacts and potential synergies with ecosystems. The goal is to facilitate societal engagement and support for wind power, enabling its contribution to the decarbonization strategy of the EU. The project aims to convert the results of comprehensive models evaluating the potential for wind power development, impacts, conflicts, and synergies into resources for stakeholders to support informed decision making and lower impact deployment of wind energy.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW AND STRATEGY

Dissemination and communication activities represent a key part of the project. These activities are to convey information about the project, to promote the achievements to all the potential interested parties, to raise awareness across multiple communication channels, ensuring publication and promotion towards different stakeholders to achieve the largest possible adoption and impact for WIMBY results.

In particular, the strategy focuses on communicating the benefits of WIMBY to end-users, in order to raise awareness and connect citizens, municipalities and local communities with industry representatives and technology providers.

Work Package 6 (WP6) is entirely dedicated to communication, dissemination and exploitation tasks: a series of specific strategies and plans, which are closely aligned with the different phases of the project, with the final aim of bringing EU-funded research and its results to the attention of multiple audiences.

The different measures aim to:

1. **Maximize the visibility of the project and its network of experts** to help gain the understanding by the local communities and key stakeholders, and support from the scientific community and policymakers;
2. **Ensure knowledge sharing and co-evaluation of solutions** with relevant communities and strategic stakeholders involved, thanks to a series of events and a forum where ideas and opinions can be exchanged;
3. **Ensure adoption of research outputs, solutions and recommendations** and uptake of the results by decision makers, health organisations, communities of citizens and the scientific community;
4. **Spread knowledge and raise awareness** by interacting with citizens and stakeholders through dedicated workshops and making the

project results openly available on the official website and on relevant open access platforms;

5. **Attract stakeholders as potential end-users of WIMBY's results**, to better understand end users-needs and provide valuable feedback on the project goals and objectives.

The dissemination task spans the whole project duration (36 months), consistently communicating the project's progress and results, and engaging and involving all the categories of target audiences identified at the early stages of the project.

The WIMBY dissemination activities are designed to match the messages to be communicated with the right target audience, with the end goal of achieving awareness across a multi-layered community. To do so, the dissemination plan is based on five pillars, each one detailed in this document:

1. **Define the key messages and the goals of dissemination:** identify the desired outcomes and the ways to achieve them. See section 2.1.
2. **Identify the different stakeholders:** find key targets interested in the project's outcomes and central for the success of it. See section 2.2.
3. **Tailor the information:** personalise the communication message based on the interests and needs of the stakeholders. Depending on the characteristics of the target audience, the communication message may vary in term of content, style and information support. See section 2.3.
4. **Identify, plan and perform the communication and coordination activities:** build a clear and coherent strategy for the project communication that takes into account the goals, the target and the specific communication for each type of audience; the strategy will help the consortium in reaching the dissemination goals and ensuring continuity and consistency in the communication activities. See section 3.
5. **Measure the impact of communication and dissemination:** identify a set of indicators (KPIs) to keep track of the dissemination activities performed by the project and to monitor the progress of the dissemination. These indicators will help to determine if the dissemination strategy is achieving the expected results. See section 4.

2.1 Communication and Dissemination goals

The WIMBY project aims to analyse wind power resources and their diverse local impacts across Europe and develop interactive engagement tools for planning and designing single projects and the sector-wide energy transition. The project adopts an inter- and transdisciplinary approach combining data-driven and participatory methods to deliver its objectives. The methodology is structured along disciplinary lines, including detailed research into the physical limits of wind resources, technical and ecological impacts, and social and economic impacts.

The project also focuses on developing solutions for an interactive engagement process with the local population and all stakeholders involved. The main activities include identifying concerns, identifying those affected and developing guidelines, best practices and remediation strategies.

The key role of WP6 is, on the one hand to support the research part interacting with citizen and stakeholders to raise awareness and social acceptance of wind energy (communication), and on the other hand, to communicate the milestones, the results and WIMBY's outcomes to ensure their uptake (dissemination) and impact on the long term. The success of the dissemination tasks is also related to the extent of the communication to the widest possible audience of stakeholders

- in the energy industry.
- in local communities that will adopt and validate the proposed collaborative and citizen-led approach for onshore and offshore wind-farm evaluation.,
- in renewable energy R&D domains who are interested in increasing the social acceptance by integrating citizens' needs in wind-farm projects.

Depending on the phase of the project and on the stakeholders expected involvement, the communication and dissemination activities' aim is to reach:

1. **Awareness** of WIMBY's activities, providing all the information about the project, promoting its achievements to all interested parties.

2. **Understanding**, by transferring key messages to specific stakeholders and enhancing their comprehension of WIMBY's outcomes.
3. **Engagement**, by interacting from the earliest stages of the project with stakeholder communities, especially citizens living in pilot cases, to promote social acceptance and awareness of wind energy processes.
4. **Use** of results, guidelines and tools developed within the WIMBY project, tailored on stakeholders needs.

2.2 Target audience

The communication of WIMBY objectives and results to a specific community of users is an inherent objective of a project that wants to create acceptance and raise public understanding and engagement by assessing impacts on local communities and addressing issues concerning governance, regulation, health impacts and intangibles.

As previously stated, strategic communication relies on the clarification of targets, audience, and message before deciding on which media the message could be transmitted. The WIMBY communication and dissemination plan is designed to match the messages to be communicated with the target audience and the means used, with the end goal of achieving awareness across a multi-layered community. This is fundamental to tailor the communication and increase the possibility of reaching the desired goals.

The WIMBY target audience has been categorised under four main clusters:

1. **Institutions, Decision Makers and PolicyMakers:** the project establishes dedicated communication channels (consultations, workshops, newsletter campaigns, etc.) and products (summarized guidelines and reports) to communicate information and ideas early and often. This ensures that policymakers are aware and informed about the adopted methodologies and results, gaining their full endorsement regarding innovative regulations and incentive schemes related to wind power production, participatory planning, siting, and deployment;
2. **Research and Innovation communities:** the project establishes an Advisory Board in coordination with task T7.2 to ensure the scientific

soundness, ethical and unbiased character of the engagement activities and the methodologies and conditions of implementation of the proposed solutions;

3. Representatives:

3.1. of the main industry and manufacturers: the project involves representatives across the wind energy value chain, from development to sale, to gain their attention and support the innovations proposed both in terms of best practices for public acceptance and related smart tools and help distribute project results in the relevant networks;

3.2. of local institutions and entities, both public and private: local authorities and local civil associations are involved in the promotion, participation and potential direct involvement of their members, to ensure there is room for them to initiate a more direct dialogue and enable civic participation;

3.3. of wind-power market related SMEs, developers, practitioners and public or semi-public companies: a specific communication and dissemination approach is undertaken to engage this specific target audience. Focus will be given to promote the advantages of WIMBY's tools and their integration in planning and engagement processes.

4. Citizens, local communities, potential consumers: WIMBY uses participatory engagement methodologies to identify and address as broad a range of users needs as possible, while also raising their awareness. Thus, the aim is to involve them in the identification of impacts, co-existence strategies and decision-making processes related with wind-power production infrastructures.

The broad range of different audience types outlined above will likely require different communication and dissemination strategies, using different styles, content types and levels of detail. In such a way, the strategy will ensure that the effort engages the target audience and produces a specific type of utilisation of results.

2.3 Communication and Dissemination approach

The WIMBY Communication and Dissemination plan will identify the most appropriate set of means for each category of stakeholder. In the previous

sections the main project goals and target audiences have been identified, the next steps will be:

- the identification of the target audience's characteristics and needs,
- the selection of the results to be communicated,
- the identification of the proper content, means, formats, and language style to get the desired outcomes in term of dissemination and communication objectives.

The communication and dissemination strategy is planned and will be carried out as a long-term activity to allow the community of reference to mature their knowledge along with the evolution of the project. A key role in the dissemination strategy is played by the **project's graphical identity**: each WIMBY's communication activity has to be clearly recognisable and easily associated to the project itself. The Consortium designed a dissemination pack for internal and external communication containing the project logo and logotype, deliverables, presentations and posters templates.

The main steps considered in the WIMBY communication and dissemination strategy concern:

- The analysis of the needs and interests of the main clusters of stakeholders presented in section 2.2, and the identification of the reactions intended to be achieved through the project communication. This will help the consortium in fitting the information to broadcast to the stakeholders' characteristics and expectations, considering that the communication is directed towards both technical and non-technical people, coming from different backgrounds.
- The definition of the content to promote related to the findings of the project. The content of the communication and dissemination will evolve during the project: in the initial phases of the project, the focus will be on the project promotion through informative means such as the social media pages and the website (communication); while the communication of technical results will be supported by more specialised means, such as scientific articles, presentation at conferences and seminars (dissemination).
- The implementation of dissemination activities based on the status of the project and target audience, the evaluation of the project and the necessities of the moment.

- The implementation of a lively stakeholder engagement strategy, as stated in the signed Grant Agreement (Wimby, 2023), where it is specified that all partners will develop a stakeholder engagement plan specifically for the purpose of ensuring their partake in the project and in the process of co-creation, validation and use of the Web-GIS interactive Forum. The adoption of a multi-layered communication approach, using the appropriate means: interpersonal and target-sensitive communication should come along with social and mass-media communication.

3. COMMUNICATION MEANS AND ACTIVITIES

The communication of the WIMBY project will be a collaborative activity managed by Deep Blue and supported by the whole consortium, to ensure an effective diffusion of information. Partners will help to identify the different target audiences and domain-specific channels in their countries. Pilot site leaders will help inform local communities about planned activities and events. Tailored messages will enhance the level of engagement, depending on the type of the target audience. Listed communication means can be easily updated throughout the duration of the project, and adapted the changing needs and additional communication goals. The communication and networking actions are divided into:

- **Communication means:** brochures, flyers, newsletters, videos and all multimedia products that can be easily sent, printed or digitally exchanged. All these materials will also be uploaded as digital resources on the project website and can be freely downloaded.
- **Dissemination means:** Scientific papers, policy briefs, white papers and reports and all other means that are specifically developed to promote project results either digitally or during workshops, conferences and events.
- **Communication and dissemination channels:** all the available web channels such as website, social networks and other online platforms either hosting contents or offering access to online means or tools for official communication and dissemination (e.g. newsletter, survey tools, scientific articles platforms, video hosting platforms, the WIMBY Web-GIS platform).
- **Communication and dissemination activities:** live events, workshops, conferences organised by the project or by consortium members promoting the project objectives and results.

3.1 Laid out multimedia

Distribution of branded multimedia products will be crucial for the project identity and recognisability. It will be pursued during organised presentations, public events, forums, and conferences, to reinforce the project messages with visual representation as well. Simultaneously, the

same products will be accessible via the website, ensuring shareability and readability to the largest audience.

3.1.1 Dissemination pack

The dissemination pack is composed of a set of products associated with the project image: the logo, the style guide and the document templates. It is developed to ensure consistency to the project communication. It will be a practical framework shared with all WIMBY consortium and updated throughout the project duration.

1. The project logo
2. The style guide
3. The document templates

Firstly, the logo was designed to offer a conceptual representation of the project, meaningful to its objectives and aesthetically appealing. At the Kick off Meeting, three logos were presented, so that partners could comment, give input, and choose their favorite.

Figure 1 – WIMBY logo 1st proposal

Figure 2 – WIMBY logo 2nd proposal

Figure 3 – WIMBY logo 3rd proposal

After collecting general impressions from the consortium members, the Deep Blue graphic team further worked on the first and most voted proposal, implementing recommended changes. The final version of the logo was consolidated in February 2023.

Figure 4 – The official WIMBY logo

The chosen logo portrays a wind turbine blade in a garden, represented by a fence and a small house. The logo includes a visual representation of the project name that is meant to convey a sense of welcome and acceptance, adopting a colour palette related with the sea (teal for offshore establishments), the land (chardonnay for onshore establishments) and of course the air (turquoise).

As second step, a style guide was outlined (See Annex I. WIMBY styleguide). It contains the colour palette, the fonts and all the graphic settings that could be necessary in the dissemination products. The creative process has been carried out by Deep Blue graphic team, but feedback was requested from the consortium.

Once the overall visual identity had been defined, it was applied to document templates (See Annex II. WIMBY ppt template). Working templates are crucial to reinforce the common language used by the project and they are easily adapted to needs of consortium partners. Templates for deliverables, presentations, and posters have been provided, together with the visual identity materials that will be used among the whole project duration. The dissemination pack includes:

- the logo in .png and vector format
- the fonts
- the style guide
- the A4 vertical word template for deliverables
- the A4 vertical word template for project meetings Agenda
- the A4 vertical word template for project meetings minutes
- the power point presentation template
- the power point project slide deck

All templates have been uploaded on the project Sharepoint for all partners to use and they will be updated, according to the versioning YYYY-MM-DD_WIMBY_[Name of document]vX.X

3.1.2 Brochures and flyers

As outreach materials for communication and dissemination during public events, printed flyers and brochures will be produced to present WIMBY's goals, outcomes and findings. The structure of the brochures can be adjusted to the type of conference and objective of the communication; they will be developed to be easily adaptable in terms of content and style. The textual content will be agreed with the partner attending the conference in advance. The brochures and flyers will always be up to date and available for download on the website.

3.1.3 Roll-up and posters

A roll-up and a project poster will be designed, based on the content used in the brochures, extended and detailed in order to better inform casual passers-by. The poster will also contain QR codes, linking to further information available online, such as pilot sites' pages, videos or other

resources. The roll-up and posters will be printed and showcased during public project events and at conferences and workshops.

3.1.4 Presentations

Laid-out presentations will be prepared for the participation in conferences, workshops, events and internal meetings. The presentations for external events should contain less textual information and will have a predominantly graphical aspect to attract the target audience. They will always include the main project references such as the link to the project website, social media pages and contacts. Presentations will be stored in dedicated repositories and made available on the website for free download. All partners will create and organize the contents, while DBL will support by providing guidelines and suggestions on how to align identity.

3.1.5 Videos

Several project videos will be delivered to disseminate project objectives, results and outcomes. Videos are well-suited to deliver information in a very effective and immediate way and are often considered one of the best options to raise awareness.

WIMBY will produce: a project video either in motion graphics or using recorded materials to showcase our goal, ambition and outcomes and 4 short video-interviews with pilot cases' stakeholders (ranging from citizens to public authorities and entrepreneurs) to collect their feedback about the engagement strategies adopted by WIMBY, to show how the research is going and what has been achieved (Multi Criteria Stakeholder Analysis, 3D environment, Web-GIS, citizen science, etc...).

Deep Blue's YouTube channel will be used to publish the videos, distributed through various channels (e.g. social networks, project and partners' websites) and, whenever possible, displayed during public events or conferences.

3.2 Communication means and activities

3.2.1 Website and news

The WIMBY website provides a comprehensive overview of project objectives, planned activities and results. It also introduces the consortium and the pilot sites, offers references to linked projects and provides an overview of news, articles, and tools. The website will be updated constantly and will represent the main dissemination activity channel: news, progresses, events, incoming workshops and any other announcement will be issued via its news section. It will also serve as a repository of relevant documents, public deliverables and scientific publications. The project partners will support this task by sharing updates about publications, participation in conferences or new project results. The interested visitors will be able to easily read through the content, download resources and get engaged via the newsletter form or social media links.

Deep Blue is responsible for the design, realisation, maintenance and update of both the website and the social network profiles. Both the structure and the external appearance of the website are developed considering the highest usability standards, ensuring a clear and easy navigation for all kinds of users and from all devices thanks to responsive design. The website structure and contents can be summarised as follows:

- Homepage – WIMBY in a nutshell, project concept image, expected results, latest news and highlighted content carousel, newsletter form
- About:
 - Project overview
 - Context and challenges – the main challenges of the project
 - Methodology and stakeholders
 - Objectives – list of the objectives linked to the results and the resources
- Pilot sites – details, current activities and focus on each pilot site
 - Pantelleria
 - Rogaland
 - Styria
 - Portugal
- Team – consortium members and their official websites
- Web-GIS and forum
 - Web-GIS (to be added in a later phase)
 - General forum + login link (to be added in a later phase)

- News and Events – the section containing all the latest news about the project and incoming events, both as participants and as organisers (news, articles, events, workshops)
- Resources – the online repository where products and digital media will be collected and free to be downloaded
 - Tools
 - Deliverables
 - Press releases
 - Scientific publications
 - Infographics and media
- Contacts – main project’s contacts
- General pages

Figure 5 – Website Architecture

From a technical point of view, in order to develop a secure, reliable and dynamic website, a professional hosting service providing a database service (MySQL) and backup features was chosen. The website has been developed using a Content Management System (CMS) technical platform that allows for an easy management of the contents and the sections of the website. Among the CMSs available, we selected the one considered the most reliable, supported from a documentation point of view and flexible, Wordpress (WWW.WORDPRESS.ORG). In order to improve the WIMBY website positioning on the major search engine, Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) functionalities were enabled. This functionality increases the possibility of

being correctly identified and proposed to users by search engines. Google Analytics tools will be used to monitor the website usage and accesses. It provides statistical information about the website: visitors, traffic sources, most viewed content, etc. It is a helpful tool to identify possible issues, increase efficiency, and evaluate the website's impact and effectiveness. To ensure the full compliance with the latest GDPR General Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament provisions (European Union, 2016), the website will refer to well known and safe services such as Iubenda (<HTTPS://WWW.IUBENDA.COM>), with Deep Blue acting as data controller. The website will only collect the personal data strictly necessary, freely provided by the users, or, in case of usage data, collected automatically when navigating the website, such as cookies and navigation flows. The additional tools delivered as project outcomes such as the WebGIS platform and the General Forum will have an access point through the project website. These tools, prior users' consent, will collect personal data such as registered users' email addresses and usernames. The technical specifications and the hosting profiles will be defined in next phases of the project, when the actual development of tools envisioned in T5.3 General Forum will kick-off.

3.2.2 Social networks

For disseminating the project outcomes, the consortium has chosen to use social media applications such as LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. These channels help open discussion around the project topics, not only among an interested and key public but also a more general public, which is a crucial part of the acceptance goal of the project. However, the effectiveness of these dissemination means will be periodically evaluated in order to compare communication strategies and get a comprehensive picture of what is working and what is not.

The three social media were chosen with different aims:

- LinkedIn, as a professional social network, attracts a group of interested professionals, stakeholders, policy makers and end-users that can exchange information and discuss about the project and its findings, and learn more about the pilot sites. The information shared via LinkedIn will be as informative as possible: thanks to the longer format that the platform allows, it will be possible to discuss certain

topics more extensively and create discussion in the comments section;

- LINKEDIN Access link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/wimby-wind-in-my-backyard/>
- Twitter supports short and focused communication, so it will be used to promote news about the project (e.g. participation to events, deliverables released, etc...), relevant information and to interact with key actors for the project, giving the possibility to retweet their status in case it is strategic for WIMBY;
- TWITTER Access link: https://twitter.com/WIMBY_project
- YouTube is a platform for publishing videos, enjoying them easily and free of charge. Deep Blue's account will be used to publish WIMBY's project and short interviews videos.
- DBL YouTube Access link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCaeQRA-jZQAiP9Nf7CuJ56Q>

As the channels strongly differ from each other, they have to be used in different ways. To ensure a successful communication, the project's tone of voice should be friendly and slightly technical, especially when content is directed towards the citizen and the general public. The attitude has to be plain but still authoritative, and informative. Using clear and concise language to explain technical concepts and ideas, will make the message easier to take in. Scientific content from the technical tasks of the project will be analysed and transformed into communicable content to be widely spread to policymakers and relevant stakeholders and communities.

Table 1 – Partners social media handles

Partners social media handles	LinkedIn	Twitter
VUB	@Vrije Universiteit Brussel	@VUBrussel
DTU	@Technical University of Denmark	@DTUtweet
IIASA	@International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)	@IIASAVienna

BOKU	@University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna (BOKU)	@BOKUvienna
UiO	@University of Oslo (UiO)	@UniOslo
NAZKA	@Nazka mapps	@nazka_mapps
UCL	@UCL	@ucl
DBL	@Deep Blue	@dblue_it
UU	@Utrecht University	@UniUtrecht
POLITO	@Politecnico di Torino	@PoliTOnews
POLIBA	@Politecnico di Bari	@PolibaOfficial
APREN	@APREN - Associação Portuguesa de Energias Renováveis	@APRENpt
PSI	@Paul Scherrer Institut PSI	@psich_en
MSC	@Multiconsult	@multiconsult_no
ETH	@ETH Zürich	@ETH_en
KIE	@The Kelso Institute Europe	N/A

Table 2 – List of official project hashtags

Official project hashtags
#Awareness
#CitizensEngagement
#Citizenship
#CleanEnergy
#ClimateChange
#Decarbonisation
#EnergyTransition
#Environment
#HorizonEU
#Offshore
#Onshore
#PilotSite
#Renewables
#RenewableEnergy
#RenewablePower
#SocialAcceptance
#Sustainability
#SustainableEnergy
#WIMBY
#Wind
#WindEnergy
#WindFarm
#WindPark

#WindPower

#WindTurbines

3.2.3 Newsletter

A bi-annual project e-newsletter will be sent to partners, key stakeholders, specific audiences and interested contacts who have subscribed to the form on the website. The newsletter's aim is to keep the audience interested and informed about activities and results, public deliverables presentation, project progression, publications, with insights, useful links, and interesting readings.

For the delivery and management of contacts – including their privacy in compliance with the GDPR regulation (EU 2016/679) – a MailerLite account will be opened. MailerLite (www.mailerlite.com) is a reliable and secure tool which guarantees transparent opt-in/opt-out choices to subscribers and supports a simple customizable design and effective delivery. In order to boost the number of subscribers, a link to a subscription form will be available on the project's website homepage. Contacts will also be collected during webinars, events and workshops, prior consent.

3.2.4 Press releases

Press releases are official statements that are sent to targeted members of the traditional news media to announce newsworthy contents or results to be promoted. A press release is a short, compelling news story, whose goal is to catch the interest of a journalist or publication. Two press releases will be shared during WIMBY's lifetime: the first at the beginning of the project (M1-12), to announce about the birth of the project, its goals and peculiarities, in order to gain visibility and start collecting followers; the second one at the end of the project (M25-36), to summarize what WIMBY accomplished in terms of acceptance of wind power solutions and in term of research and development of new useful tools. When feasible, press releases will be translated in the national languages of the consortium partners and will be distributed to press agencies of their countries to ensure a wider circulation of the information. All partners will be asked to share potential press-contacts in their domain, network and geographical area, publishing both online and on paper, both in English and in their local

language, in order to reach out for the highest number of audiences and individuals.

3.2.5 WIMBY General Forum

The WIMBY General Forum will be a cross-domain tool linked with the Web-GIS platform, involving local citizens, energy communities, NGOs, authorities, users' representatives, consumers, policymakers, technology providers, business and industry representatives. In this forum participants can exchange information and provide inputs to one another and identify the effect of the implemented models on promoting wind energy, collaborate on solutions, exchanging experiences and establishing cross-sectoral collaborations. This process is framed in outreach activities to promote social awareness and engagement on wind energy, which serves to develop guidelines for participatory processes in wind farm development. To this end, the Web-GIS interactive forum will facilitate the identification of future areas for deployment based on validated models and holistic assessment metrics, which allow to reach interactive and mutually value enhancing outcomes for the participating stakeholders. The Advisory Board, which will be established by bringing together key stakeholders and domain experts, will support the continuous engagement of the General Forum members. All T5.3 partners, namely NAZKA, DTU, VUB and BOKU will support the forum design, co-creation, development and maintenance both in terms of content and technical aspects and in close collaboration with WP6 activities.

3.2.6 Internal communication

The internal communication strategy will focus on raising interaction and knowledge transfer between partners and ensure the success of the project. All partners will interact regularly and periodic updates will be provided during planned General Assemblies and Executive board meetings; additional meetings will be organized when needed by the WP leaders to ensure fruitful and open exchange within the whole Consortium. Further multi- and bi-lateral contacts will be held with other partners. Furthermore, the project will make use of a number of project management tools to maximise the effectiveness of internal communication and collaboration between partners, such as:

- the SHAREPOINT document management system that will be used as shared file repository for the whole consortium.
- a set of appropriate project mailing lists that facilitate the communication and the exchange of information:
 - ga@wimby.eu (General Assembly: all the main contacts of each partner)
 - finances@wimby.eu (all admin and finances contacts)
 - eb@wimby.eu (EB group contacts)
 - consortium@wimby.eu (full consortium contacts)
- a customised Mattermost open source and secure platform dedicated to facilitate real-time communication, file and code snippet sharing, in-line code syntax highlighting, and workflow automation purpose-built for technical teams (<https://mattermost.com>). A specific structure will be created to allow project teams (on WP, Task and topic level) to work efficiently together. The Project Coordinator, with the support of Deep Blue as communication leader, is responsible for the management of the platform and costs related to it. DTU is responsible for the technical management and updates of the Mattermost IT infrastructure.
- teleconferences and video conferences systems for periodic update meetings.

Efficacy, timeliness, and ease of interaction are the main objectives of this activity: any issues and inconveniences will be promptly addressed and solved to ensure continuity.

3.3 Dissemination activities

The dissemination means and activities described in this section aim to enhance the outreach of project results and make scientific results a common good and maximise the project impact.

3.3.1 Dissemination towards the Advisory Board

Active contribution and participation from a large set of stakeholders are key aspects for the achievement of WIMBY's objectives. The consortium including partners and associated partners will be supported by an effective and meaningful Advisory Board already mentioned in D7.1 Project Handbook (WIMBY, 2023) that includes:

ENGIE, Renewable Energy BeLux, Siemens, Gamesa Renewable Energy, EDP renewables S.A., Greek Public Power Corporation S.A., Greenventory GmbH, TwingTec, PostdamInstitute for Advanced Sustainability Studies, European Renewable Energies Federation, Canada Research Chair in Urban Planning for Climate Change, FinergeS.A., EDA Renováveis, S.A., Ventient Energy.

Ad-hoc meetings and consultations will be organised to collect Advisory Board members opinions and feedback, in collaboration with the scientific coordination team and work package leaders, as described in D7.1.

3.3.2 Coordination and networking with other EU funded action

To ensure its success and visibility, the WIMBY project needs to collaborate and create synergies with other projects and initiatives in the Horizon Europe Programme framework. Collaborating with projects that have similar goals or are in the same field of research can be significant to WIMBY’s success. Sharing results and networking can help the project’s growth, contribute to the research of sister projects in the field, create real synergies and explore the possibility of coordinating the dissemination activity or better organising the research.

Table 3 – List of R&I projects contacted by WIMBY – Sister projects

List of R&I projects contacted by WIMBY – Sister projects	
JUSTWIND4ALL. Just and effective governance for accelerating wind energy	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101083936
WENDY. Multicriteria analysis of the technical, environmental and social factors triggering the PIMBY principle for Wind technologies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084137

A preliminary list of potentially interesting research and innovation projects has been compiled and will be monitored during the project lifetime:

Table 4 – List of R&I projects monitored by WIMBY

List of R&I projects and initiatives monitored by WIMBY	
SCORE (Supporting Consumer Co-Ownership in Renewable Energies)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/784960/results

DECIDE (Developing Energy Communities through Informative and collective actions)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/894255/it https://decide4energy.eu/
Agro Fossil Free and Area Zero Cluster	https://www.agrofossilfree.eu/

3.3.3 Dissemination towards the European Commission

Institutional EU websites will be used to promote the project results at a European level to policy makers, researchers, and a vast variety of experts. The Consortium plans to appear at least twice on one of the following channels:

- Horizon Magazine: the EU research and Innovation Magazine spreading the latest news and features about science and innovative research projects funded by the EU.
- Research and Innovation Success Stories: a collection of the most recent success stories from EU-funded Research & Innovation.
- CORDIS: Multilingual articles and publications that highlight research results, based on an open repository of EU project information.
- BRIDGE or ETIP-SNET Newsletter

3.3.4 Project events and workshops

Public events and workshops are effective means for involving stakeholders and end-users in an effective and successful communication campaign. Feedback from these sessions will be used to improve WIMBY methodology, end users' participation and wind farm social acceptance.

- **12 (twelve) total workshops engaging local citizens and further stakeholders in pilot cases** will be organized from M18 to M34 and they will showcase the WIMBY approach and solutions to key stakeholder groups, unlocking business opportunities in established and emerging markets worldwide and focusing on transitional justice and on the goals to foster energy citizenship. A local partner for each pilot sites supports data collection for WP1, WP2 and WP4, contributes to the work of DBL in producing customised materials, ensures that stakeholders choose to partake in the co-creation, validation and active use of the Web-GIS and the interactive forum and is responsible for the organisation of on-site and hybrid workshops. Up to three workshops are held in each pilot depending on the local circumstances, including the co-creation

process of the tools, the MCSA, stakeholder mapping, economic experiments, and the consolidation of the General Forum foreseen in WP5. These workshops have the following characteristics:

- 1. Open Days:** Involvement of stakeholders, interest groups, and interested members of the local public in each pilot case to collect qualitative as well as quantitative data through questionnaires and feedback on the interactive Web-GIS forum in the second year of the project: 1 or 2 focus group workshops (in different locations) with two or three sessions per day.
 - 2. Detailed pilot site research workshops:** Involvement of the local population at a specific pilot site with detailed results from the "open days". Workshops also organised in more days to involve different groups such as school classes, concerned citizens, local politics and further local stakeholders.
 - 3. Closing Workshops:** Continuation of the involvement of the local population at a specific case study site: 1 half or full day workshop with local stakeholders (aiming for the same participants as the previous workshops). Lessons learned are presented and a final MCSA exercise is conducted to discuss stakeholders' needs and priorities.
- **3 (three) Advisory Board workshops** will be organised to steer the project activities and validate project outcomes around M9, M20 and M32. All relevant stakeholder groups will be invited to attend key project events and demonstrations, discussing WIMBY activities and results from their specific perspectives and gathering their feedback. VUB will lead the task and support the creation of the Advisory Board group as described in D7.1 Project Handbook and will conduct local workshops. DBL will design the workshops and support their execution.
 - **A mid-project public event** organised around M22 to promote first project outcomes across the different stakeholders at the EU level.
 - **A Final public event** at the end of the project (between M32 and M36) that reaches out to EC officials, policy makers, main actors of the different market sectors and related industries.

Partners conducting the workshops will use tailored communication materials and templates designed by DBL to reach the targeted stakeholders and rely on the assistance from the pilot cases leaders and their collaboration network that includes, among others, local (planning) authorities and wind power project developers.

3.3.5 Third parties' events and conferences

All consortium members are committed to look for, take part in and/or attend both European and international networking conferences and domain specific fairs and events, in order to disseminate WIMBY's advancements and results. The objective is to help raise awareness on the potential beneficial impacts of the project among a specialised audience and enlarge the pool of stakeholders.

WIMBY has to deliver three lectures as in person or online seminars involving academic partners and, whenever it is possible, including the possibility of testing the Web-GIS interactive forum and the immersive 3D environments.

The project also plans to take part in events to disseminate its results, share information and create synergies with other relevant projects and initiatives organised in the framework of CINEA such as BRIDGE, ETIP-SNET and similar initiatives.

A preliminary list of events and conferences can be found below. Further events will be identified during the project.

Table 5 – List of external events and conferences

External events and conferences		
Madrid, Spain	AWEC: Airborne Wind Energy Conference https://awec2024.com/	24 – 26 April 2024
Lappeenranta, Finland	EEM23: International Conference on European Energy Markets https://www.lut.fi/en/eem23	6 – 8 June 2023
Vienna, Austria & Online	EGU: European Geoscience Union https://www.egu24.eu/	14 – 19 April 2024
Gdynia, Poland	EUROLAG10 Conference https://eurolag10.mir.gdynia.pl/	19 – 23 June 2023
Brussels, Belgium & Online	EUSEW: European Sustainable Energy Week https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en	20 – 22 June 2023

Istanbul, Turkey	IAEE: International Conference https://www.iaee.org/en/conferences/	25 – 28 June 2024
Doha, Qatar	ICAE: International conferences on Applied Energy https://applied-energy.org/icae2023/icae2023.jpg	3 – 7 December 2023
Prague, Czechia	ICEEEP: International Conference on Energy Economics and Energy Policy http://www.iceeep.com/	6 – 7 September 2024
Lisbon, Portugal	Lisbon Energy Summit & Exhibition 2023 https://www.lisbonenergysummit.com/	30 May – 01 June 2023
Lisbon, Portugal	Oceanic Renewables Summit https://www.apren.pt/en/conferences/apren-oceanic-renewables-summit/about/	24 May 2023
Lisbon, Portugal	Portugal Renewable Energy Summit (APREN)	November 29 & 30, 2023
Melbourne, Australia	OMAE: International Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering https://event.asme.org/OMAE	11 – 16 June 2023
Catania, Italy	S.It.E.: Congresso della Società Italiana di Ecologia https://www.ecologia.it/congressi/xxxii-congresso-prima-circolare/	6 – 8 September 2023
Glasgow, UK	WESC: The Wind Energy Science Conference https://www.wesc2023.eu/	23 – 26 May 2023
Hamburg, Germany	WindEnergy Hamburg https://www.windenergyhamburg.com/en/	24 – 27 September 2024
Bilbao, Spain	WindEurope: https://windeurope.org/annual2024/	20 – 22 March 2024
Belfast, UK	British Ecological Society annual meeting: https://www.britishecologicalsociety.org/events/bes-annual-meeting-2023/welcome-to-bes2023/	12 – 15 December 2023
Sevilla, Spain	SETAC Europe 34th Annual Meeting: https://www.setac.org/events/eventdetails.aspx?id=1666656	5–9 May 2024
Lisbon, Portugal	Oceanic Renewables Summit	May 2024 TBC
Lisbon, Portugal	Portugal Renewable Energy Summit	November 2024 (TBC)

3.3.1 Scientific articles and papers

During the lifetime of the project, 12 scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals will be released: six during the second year (M13-24) and the remaining six in the third year (M25-36). Scientific and technical publications will seek for publication in major peer-reviewed scientific journals to ensure the quality and accuracy of the research. Also, two articles in general and domain related press and magazines about interesting aspects of WIMBY’s research and results will be published to raise awareness among the general and interested public. Scientific publications will be evaluated by experts in the field and are considered of high quality. To ensure good visibility for the scientific papers and articles, following the guidelines presented by Springer publishing in the article “Maximize your visibility. Promoting your research effectively”¹ is recommended. This process will increase the visibility and impact of the research, as it is more likely to be cited and referenced by other researchers.

WIMBY will follow the European guidelines on the large-scale accessibility of project findings. Gold open access publishing will be granted to all scientific publications resulting from the project. However, all articles resulting from WIMBY will also be available on the project website.

Table 6 – List of scientific journals

Scientific peer reviewed journals		Peer reviewed
Scientific peer reviewed journal about environmental science	Energy & Environmental Science https://www.rsc.org/journals-books-databases/about-journals/energy-environmental-science	Yes
Policy implications of energy supply	Energy Policy https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-policy	Yes
Open peer review journal	Energy Strategy Reviews https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-strategy-reviews	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed	Energy, Sustainability and Society https://energysustainsoc.biomedcentral.com/	Yes

¹ <https://www.springernature.com/gp/researchers/publication-promotion#c19043898>. Last access on May 2023

journal about energy		
Scientific peer reviewed journal about impact assessment	Environmental Impact Assessment Review https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/environmental-impact-assessment-review	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed journal about sustainable energy solution	Joule https://www.cell.com/joule/home	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed journal	Nature Sustainability https://www.nature.com/natsustain/	Yes
Open peer review for EU research projects	Open Research Europe https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed journal	Nature Energy https://www.nature.com/nenergy/	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed journal on energy engineering	Applied Energy https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/applied-energy	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed paper on all important energy topics	Energy Conversion and Management https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-conversion-and-management	Yes
Peer-reviewed academic journal on futures studies, technology assessment, and technological forecasting	Technological Forecasting and Social Change https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/technological-forecasting-and-social-change	Yes
Scientific peer reviewed journal on economic and	Energy Economics https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-economics	Yes

econometric modelling and analysis of energy systems and issues		
Journal addressing various environmental topics	Science of Total Environment: https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/science-of-the-total-environment	Yes
Journal on circular economy and sustainability	Journal of Industrial Ecology: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/15309290	Yes
Scientific journal looking at interface between biological systems and aspects of environmental change	Global Change Biology https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/13652486	Yes
Journal that focuses explicitly on the ecological understanding of spatial heterogeneity	Landscape Ecology	Yes
Journal focusing on wind resources, wakes and optimization	Wind Energy Sciences https://www.wind-energy-science.net/	Yes

Table 7 - List of general and domain related magazines

General and domain related magazines		Printed/Online
Sustainable energy	Balkan Green Energy News https://balkangreenenergynews.com/	Online
EC's primary source of results	CORDIS: EU Research Results https://cordis.europa.eu/	Online

from R&I projects		
Renewable energy sector	Energy Global https://www.energyglobal.com/	Online
Energy and transport	European Energy Innovation http://www.europeanenergyinnovation.eu/	Online
News about global energy transition	Foresight Climate & Energy https://foresightdk.com/	Online
News	Innovation News Network https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/	Online
News	POLITICO https://www.politico.eu/	Online
News about Renewables	Renewable Energy https://www.renewableenergymagazine.com/	Online
News about Renewables	Renewables Now https://renewablesnow.com/	Online
Sustainable energy	Revolve https://revolve.media/	Online
News in the power and energy sectors	The Energy Industry Time https://teitimes.com/	Printed

Table 8 – List of EC channels for dissemination of results

EC Channels for dissemination of results	
CORDIScovery https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/428991-introducing-the-cordiscovery-podcast-a-new-way-to-keep-up-with-eu-research-results	CORDIS’ monthly podcast that dives into some of the key scientific solutions being developed by EU-funded researchers
Innovation radar: https://www.innoradar.eu/	An initiative that identifies high-potential innovations, based on a data-driven methodology, and assists EU-funded researchers and innovators in reaching the market with their innovation.
Open Research Europe platform: https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/	An open access, publishing platform for scientific papers for Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe beneficiaries, including an open peer review and article revision.

Horizon Results platform: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform	A platform for showcasing your research results, finding collaboration opportunities and getting inspired by the results of others.
Horizon Results Booster: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/d-e-booster	Free consulting services including a portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development and go-to-market support.
European Standardisation Booster Service for EU Projects: https://www.hsbooster.eu/	Supports Horizon Europe and H2020 projects to contribute to standardisation in Europe and beyond.

4. MONITORING AND KPIS

Monitoring a series of dissemination activities is a critical aspect of achieving success and maximizing the impact of any communication strategy. By monitoring a communication campaign, WIMBY can assess the effectiveness of its messages, adjust its strategies based on real-time feedback, and ultimately achieve its communication objectives. Additionally, monitoring a communication activity helps to identify areas for improvement, which can develop future steps.

However, it is important to set some measures, which will be used to know if this dissemination strategy is achieving its aims. Several KPIs have been identified to keep track of the progress of the dissemination. Table 9 below presents a cumulative list of all dissemination and communication Key Performance Indicators for the WIMBY project, corresponding to activities and measures presented in the plan.

Table 9 – KPIs for communication and dissemination activities

WIMBY's communication and dissemination KPIs	Phase 1 (M1-M12)	Phase 2 (M13-M24)	Phase 3 (M25-M36)	Overall
Public events organised for external audience	0	1	1	2
External events attended presenting the project	3	3	3	9
Workshops	4	5	5	14
Local events/activities organised using the local language	4	4	4	12
Number of participants to organised external public events (in person + online)	50	150	150	350
Ratio of recurring participants to in person events	1%	5%	10%	10%
Ratio of recurring participants to online events	1%	5%	5%	5%
Presentations at peer-reviewed international conferences and workshops	3	4	6	13
Scientific publication in peer-reviewed journals	0	6	6	12

News from the project (blog + social media)	10	20	20	50
Articles published on general press/magazines	0	1	1	2
Press releases delivered to traditional media	1	0	1	2
Number of unique visitors to the website	1200	1000	1800	4000
Number of references in other websites	10	20	20	50
Number of resources download	10	10	30	50
Newsletter subscribers	50	50	100	200
Large communication campaigns	1	0	1	2
Infographics for different target audience groups	1	1	1	3
Project video	1	0	0	1
Short video-interviews with pilot cases' stakeholders	0	2	2	4

These measures can be refined, updated, and integrated during the project evolution, according to the needs that may be encountered during WIMBY's course.

5. EDITORIAL PLAN

Planning an editorial plan for WIMBY’s communication and dissemination activities can help organise the work between partners, communicate more effectively, maximize the reach, and build a strong, recognisable message of the project. Taking the time to plan WIMBY’s communication and dissemination approach ensures that the efforts are well-coordinated and aligned with project’s goals and objectives.

The editorial plan below is an indicative division of time, during the course of the project it may change and be more precise depending on the planned activities.

Table 10 - Preliminary editorial plan (M03-M12)

Editorial plan (M03-M12)	
March	Social media pages
	Landing page
	Communication and Dissemination Plan first draft
April	Website development and social media set up
May	Website launch + first social media posts + blogpost
June	1 st project press release
	1 st newsletter
	Website article + social media posts focused on the project approach and methodologies towards large wind deployment citizen engagement and acceptance
	Planning of a communication campaign
July	Website article + social media posts
	Planning of a first communication campaign
August	Website article + social media posts
	Launch of the 1 st Advisory Board meeting
September	Website article + social media posts
	Launch of 1 st communication campaign
October	Two website articles + social media posts
November	Website article + social media posts
	First project infographic
December	2 nd newsletter
	Website article + social media posts

All partners will be required to provide inputs and information to write the articles and to feed the website and the social media pages. They will be supported by DBL in content creation and copy writing.

6. IMPACT MONITORING

6.1 Key impact pathways

With a new level of ambition to boost the diversity of the impacts of EU research and innovation funding, Horizon Europe incorporates a novel approach to capturing and communicating impacts – Key Impact Pathways (KIP). The objective of this approach is to enable policy makers and the wider public to gain regular insights into the effects and benefits of the Programme over time in relation to European science, economy and the wider society.

In that regard, WIMBY designed a monitoring and evaluation system with the goal to keep track of project achievements contributing towards the Key Impact Pathways (KIP).

Code	Name	Area	WP6 KPIs	Activity
KIP 1	Creating high quality new knowledge	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed international conferences & workshops 	Dissemination
KIP 2	Fostering the diffusion of knowledge and open science	Scientific	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals • Scientific publications in peer-reviewed international conferences & workshops • Scientific publications as Open Access 	Dissemination

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large public events organized for external audiences • External events attended representing the project 	
KIP 3	Addressing Union policy priorities and global challenges through R&I	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications through EC’s channels • Workshops (and AB) 	Dissemination
KIP 4	Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liaising activities with EU-funded projects 	Dissemination
KIP 5	Strengthening the uptake of R&I in society	Societal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General press/magazine articles published • Press releases delivered to traditional media • References in other websites • Webinars • Workshops • Public Events 	Communication
KIP 6	Generating innovation-based growth	Economic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint and individual exploitation activities 	Exploitation

6.2 Website and social media channels

After the project end, the website will be updated with the latest information and resources available. It will be maintained for two more years. Similarly, the social media profiles will follow-up communication

about most recent results and newsworthy updates. Moreover, a closing blogpost will inform the audience about the project's legacy.

ANNEXES

I. WIMBY styleguide

WIMBY STYLEGUIDE

LOGO

B/W

COLORED

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

2

LOGO

HORIZONTAL

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

3

LOGO

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

4

TYPOGRAPHY

COMFORTAA
Titles

**LOREM
IPSUM**

lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed diam nonummy nibh euismod tincidunt ut laoreet dolore magna aliquam erat velutpat. Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exerci tation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum irure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis ut vero eros et accumsan et justo odio dignism qui blandit praesent luptatum zzril delenit augue duis dolore te feugait nulla facilisi.

Poppins
Texts

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

5

COLOR PALETTE

CARROT
#FF7538

CHARDONNAY
#FFB669

TURQUOISE
#40E0D0

TEAL
#008080

LIGHT GREEN
#90EE90

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

6

DECORATIVE ELEMENTS

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

7

MOCKUPS & APPLICATIONS

WIMBY - STYLEGUIDE

8

II. WIMBY ppt template

WIMBY
Presentation layout

Mario Rossi
Professional Title

1

Section 1
- Lorem Ipsum

Add subtitle

2

Insert title here
Subtitle

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Morbi varius lorem nibh, a dictum purus luctus pharetra. Nulla eu blandit sapien. Donec vitae magna finibus, imperdiet sem ut, elementum massa. Aliquam iaculis sapien ac quam viverra tincidunt. Etiam ultrices tortor sit amet libero pellentesque, nec tempor magna convallis. Cras nec arcu sit amet felis sollicitudin euismod id eget enim. Sed placerat turpis sed metus posuere, id fringilla erat efficitur. Sed efficitur nisi ipsum, eu tempor turpis aliquam eu.

3

4

III. WIMBY deliverable template

HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME – TOPIC HORIZON-CL5-2021-D3-03-05
Wind energy in the natural and social environment
Research and Innovation action (RIA)

WIMBY
Wind in My Backyard: Using holistic modelling tools to advance social awareness and engagement on large wind power installations in the EU

Grant Agreement No. 101083460
Starting date: 1st January 2023 – Duration: 36 months

Deliverable DX.X
Title of Deliverable

WIMBY | DX.X Title of deliverable | V X.X | Dissemination level [P/C]

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Deliverable number	DX.X
Deliverable title	xxxxxx
Work Package	WPX
Deliverable type ¹	xxxxxx
Dissemination level ²	xxxxxx
Due date	dd.mm.yyyy (Month X)
Pages	XX
Document version ³	X.Y
Lead author(s)	Name, Organisation (short name)
Contributors	Name, Organisation (short name)

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1: Type: ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot; R: Report; D: Demonstrator
2: Dissemination level: C: Confidential; P: Public
3: First digit: 0: draft; 1: peer review; 2: peer review; 3: coordinator approval; 4: final version

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